

Supporting Information

Thiophene-Based Trimers for In-Vivo Electronic Functionalization of Tissues

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1. Materials and Methods

Deuterated solvent and NMR tubes were bought from Eurisotop. 3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene (EDOT) was bought from TCI. Sodium hydride dispersion 60% in mineral oil was used and bought from Sigma Aldrich. All other chemicals were supplied from Fisher Scientific. NMR spectra were recorded at ambient temperature with a 400 MHz Bruker Avance Spectrometer. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was carried out on aluminum pre-coated plates (silica gel 40-60Å 400 mesh, F254, Aldrich) using hexane:ethyl acetate (Hex:AcOEt) as eluent. High-purity grade silica gel with a pore size 60 Å, 230-400 mesh particle size, 40-63 µm particle size was bought from Sigma-Aldrich and used for flash column chromatography. High resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) has been measured by direct injection in a QStar - ABSciex, using a Q-TOF detector and positive electrospray ionization ESI⁺.

Oxidative polymerization. 1.5 equivalents of ammonium persulfate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ and a catalytic amount of FeCl_3 were dissolved in 2 mL of DI water. 10 mg of trimer were added to this solution and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 18 hours. The formation of dark green dispersions indicates that polymerization has been accomplished.

Electrochemical characterizations and polymerizations were performed with a Princeton Applied Research VersaSTAT 3 potentiostat/galvanostat using a three-electrode configuration where a platinum/titanium wire was used as the counter electrode, an ITO-coated glass substrate (with an area of 1.0 cm^2 and resistance of $10 \Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$) was used as the working electrode, and Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) was used as the reference electrode. A 0.1 M solution of tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate in acetonitrile was used as the electrolyte. For the electropolymerization reactions 1 mM of monomer dissolved in acetonitrile was used. Scans between 0 V and 1 V were performed, using a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} .

UV-vis-NIR absorption spectra were obtained using a Perkin Elmer Lambda 950 instrument. Spectra were recorded between 300 nm and 1300 nm, using a quartz cuvette, after diluting 10 times the reaction batch.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements were performed on a Bruker Alpha-II FTIR spectrometer. Spectra were collected from 4000 to 250 cm^{-1} with the following settings: 42 scans per sample and spectral resolution: 4 cm^{-1} .

Conductivity measurements were performed using a Jandel RM3-AR four-point probing system. For these measurements drop casted films were prepared using 1.5 cm diameter round glass coverslips and 0.15 mL of freshly prepared polymer dispersion. The films were

let to dry at room temperature overnight. The conductivity values were derived after probing three different films, in more than three different areas per film.

AFM measurements: The surface morphology of the electropolymerized films was characterized by atomic force microscopy (AFM) using a Dimension FastScan AFM (Bruker) in tapping mode. Silicon cantilevers (Fastscan-A) with a typical tip radius of ≈ 5 nm were used. The resonance frequency of the cantilevers was ≈ 1.40 kHz.

Note concerning polymerization: It is important to note that these trimers tend to polymerize at laboratory conditions, due to their lower oxidation onset with respect to EDOT and the presence of the ionic part which (directly or indirectly) induces doping. Therefore, the removal of solvent could result problematic and long. For this reason, it is strongly recommended to keep these molecules in the freezer. In Section 7 of Supporting Information we provide a UV-vis absorption study of the self-polymerization of EEE-S after 1,5 and 10 hours of reaction (Figure S18).

2. Synthesis & NMRs

2.1 Dibromuration of **1** and **2**

Scheme S1. Synthesis of (**3** and **4**)

The synthesis has been performed as reported in literature.^{1,2} Briefly: 2-(thiophen-3-yl)ethan-1-ol (**1**) or (2,3-dihydrothieno[3,4-b][1,4]dioxin-2-yl)methanol (**2**) (14.1 mmol) was dissolved in N,N'-Dimethylformamide (DMF) (20 mL). NBS (5.27 g, 29.6 mmol) was added and the solution was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. The resulting suspension was poured into water, then extracted with diethyl ether, and the organic phase was dried over sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford a yellowish oil/pale white solid: yield 75%/63%.

3, ¹H NMR (400 MHz, Chloroform-d) δ 6.87 (s, 1H), 3.80 (t, J = 6.5 Hz, 2H), 2.80 (t, J = 6.5 Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, Chloroform-d) δ 139.26, 131.41, 110.99, 109.58, 61.95, 32.91; R_f (Hexane:EtOAc 7:3)=0.78

4, ^1H NMR (400 MHz, Chloroform- d) δ 4.34 (dd, $J = 11.6, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 4.31 – 4.25 (m, 1H), 4.22 – 4.12 (m, 1H), 3.99 – 3.83 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, Chloroform- d) δ 139.6, 139.5, 85.7, 74.4, 66.2, 61.5; Rf (Hexane:EtOAc 1:1)=0.30

2.2 Synthesis of EDOT boronic acid pinacol ester (5)

The boronation of EDOT has been performed as reported in literature. Briefly, (2 g, 14 mmol) of EDOT was introduced in dry THF (30 mL) under an argon flow. Then, a solution of n-BuLi 2.5 M in hexane (6.2 mL, 15.5 mmol) was added dropwise at -78 °C. Afterwards, the temperature was slowly increased to 0 °C and the mixture was stirred for 30 min. Lastly, 5.6 ml (28 mmol) of 2-isopropoxy-4,4,5,5'-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolane were added at -78 °C. The reaction mixture was let to reach slowly room temperature and further stirring continued overnight. For purification, the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated NH_4Cl and extracted with diethyl ether (Et_2O) (3x100 mL). The collected organic phases were washed with water and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 . After removal of the solvent, the crude oily product was dried under vacuum. Lastly, trituration of the crude product with methanol gave pure EDOT boronic acid pinacol ester a sa white powder. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.56 (s, 1H), 4.25 – 4.20 (m, 2H), 4.13 – 4.08 (m, 2H), 1.27 (s, 12H).

2.3 Suzuki Coupling Reactions (Trimer-OHs)(6,7)

Scheme S2. Synthesis of (6 and 7)

Trimer-OHs (6 and 7) were synthesized via Suzuki coupling reactions (Scheme S2). One equivalent of 2-(2,5-dibromothiophen-3-yl)ethan-1-ol (3) (200 mg) or (5,7-dibromo-2,3-dihydrothieno[3,4-b][1,4]dioxin-2-yl)methanol (360 mg) (4) and two equivalents of EDOT boronic acid pinacol ester (5) (375 and 584 mg, respectively) were dissolved in Toluene/Methanol mixture (1:1) (60 ml and 80 ml, respectively), in a flame dried schlenk flask. The solutions were degassed (through the septum by needle) with slight flow of argon for 15 min. Then, 600 mg and 1.8 g of K₂CO₃, respectively, were added to the reactions in one portion. The reaction mixtures were heated to 40 °C and kept at 40 °C for 10 min to increase the solubility of K₂CO₃ in the mixture. Lastly, 23 and 54 mg (respectively) of PEPPSI™-IPr catalyst (5% mol of 3 and 4), were added, the flasks were sealed, and the reaction temperature increased to 75 °C for 4 h. The reaction mixtures were then poured onto the

water and extracted with dichloromethane (CH_2Cl_2) (3×50 ml). The collected organic phases were washed with brine, dried over MgSO_4 and evaporated under vacuum. The crude products were purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel hexane:EtOAc (1:1) and gave Trimer-OHs (**6** and **7**) in the form of yellowish viscous liquids with 50 and 55% yields, respectively.

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectrum of (**6**) in d_6 -DMSO

Figure S2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of (6) in d_6 -DMSO

Figure S3. ^1H NMR spectrum of (7) in d_6 -DMSO

Figure S4. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of (7) in $\text{d}_6\text{-DMSO}$

Figure S5. ATR-FTIR spectra of (6) (red, upper curve) and (7) (black, lower curve)

2.4 Synthesis of ETE-S (**10**)

Scheme S3. Synthesis of (**10**)

2-(2,5-bis(2,3-dihydrothieno[3,4-b][1,4]dioxin-5-yl)thiophen-3-yl)ethan-1-ol (**6**) 0.120 g (0.294 mmol) was dissolved in 12 ml of anhydrous DMF. Then, NaH 60% 0.013g (0.325 mmol, 1.3eq) was added and let stirring under nitrogen at room temperature for 4 hours. 1,4-Butanesultone (**8**) 60 μ L (0.080g, 0.588 mmol, 2eq) was added and the reaction mixture was then stirred overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured onto the diethyl ether and the precipitated substance was collected and washed with abundant solvent, to afford a yellowish fine powder with 77% yield (0.128g). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 7.13 (s, 1H), 6.70 (s, 1H), 6.56 (s, 1H), 4.60 – 4.20 (m, 8H), 3.55 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2H), 3.37 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 2H), 2.86 (3, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2H), 2.40 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H), 1.66 – 1.51 (m, 4H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 141.78, 141.49, 138.32, 137.85, 136.36, 132.86, 126.18, 125.01, 110.42, 108.49, 99.42, 97.47, 69.91, 69.70, 65.04, 64.77, 64.27, 64.16, 51.26, 29.44, 28.61, 22.03. HRMS (ESI) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_8\text{Na}_2\text{S}_4$, 589.00657; found, 589.00594.

Figure S6. ^1H NMR spectrum of (10) in d_6 -DMSO

Figure S7. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of (10) in d_6 -DMSO

2.5 Synthesis of ETE-N (**11**)

Scheme S4. Synthesis of (**11**)

2-(2,5-bis(2,3-dihydrothieno[3,4-b][1,4]dioxin-5-yl)thiophen-3-yl)ethan-1-ol (**6**) 0.100 g (0.245 mmol) was dissolved in 12 ml of anhydrous DMF. Then, NaH 60% 0.0069g (1.715 mmol, 7eq) was added and let stirring under nitrogen at room temperature for 4 hours. 2-Chloro-N,N-dimethylethylamine hydrochloride (**9**) 0.046g (0.319 mmol, 1.3eq) was added and the reaction mixture was then stirred overnight at room temperature. The solvent was then evaporated and the residue was dissolved in a solution Hexane:Acetonitrile 1:9 together with 0.5mL of Iodomethane. Stirring continued overnight at room temperature. The solution was poured onto the diethyl ether and a brownish precipitate was collected and washed with abundant solvent, to afford **11** in a 54% yield (0.082g).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 7.13 (s, 1H), 6.72 (s, 1H), 6.59 (s, 1H), 4.40 – 4.20 (m, 8jH), 3.90 – 3.80 (m, 2H), 3.70 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 3.53 (dd, $J = 5.7, 3.5$ Hz, 2H), 3.06 (s, 9H), 2.93 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 142.27, 142.02, 138.84, 138.37, 136.59, 133.45, 126.90, 125.18, 110.81, 108.86, 99.95, 98.08, 70.31, 65.56, 65.28, 65.00, 64.76, 64.65,

64.37, 53.55, 29.62. HRMS (ESI) m/z: [M]⁺ calcd for C₂₃H₂₈O₅N₁S₃, 494.11241; found, 494.11149.

Figure S8. ¹H NMR spectrum (**11**) in d₆-DMSO

Figure S9. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of (**11**) in d_6 -DMSO

2.6 Synthesis of *EEE-S* (**12**)

Scheme S5. Synthesis of (**12**)

(2,2',2'',3,3',3''-hexahydro-[5,5':7',5''-terthieno[3,4-b][1,4]dioxin]-2'-yl)methanol (**7**) 0.050 g (0.110 mmol) was dissolved in 7 ml of anhydrous DMF. Then, NaH 60% 0.0057g (0.144 mmol, 1.3eq) was added and let stirring under nitrogen at room temperature for 4 hours.

1,4-Butanesultone (**8**) 29 μ L (0.039g, 0.287 mmol, 2eq) was added and the reaction mixture was then stirred overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured onto the diethyl ether and the precipitated substance was collected and washed with abundant solvent, to afford a yellowish fine powder with 84% yield (0.056g). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 6.64 – 6.50 (m, 2H), 4.52 – 3.94 (m, 10H), 3.67 (dd, J = 11.3, 5.1 Hz, 1H), 3.64 – 3.57 (m, 1H), 3.50 (q, J = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.47 – 3.40 (m, 1H), 3.40 – 3.38 (m, 1H), 2.47 – 2.35 (m, 2H), 1.78 – 1.47 (m, 4H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 141.85, 141.80, 141.57, 141.51, 141.44, 141.25, 141.14, 137.43, 137.25, 137.19, 137.04, 136.57, 136.52, 109.38, 109.34, 109.30, 109.26, 109.23, 107.45, 107.36, 100.13, 98.80, 98.41, 98.11, 98.02, 73.79, 73.68, 72.97, 72.94, 71.48, 71.27, 68.97, 68.94, 68.89, 66.55, 66.50, 66.00, 65.89, 65.56, 65.44, 64.73, 51.71, 51.68, 29.01, 28.89, 22.39. HRMS (ESI) m/z: [M + Na]⁺ calcd for C₂₃H₂₃O₁₀Na₂S₄, 632.99640; found, 632.99576.

Figure S10. ¹H NMR spectrum of (**12**) in d₆-DMSO

Figure S11. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of (12) in d_6 -DMSO

Figure S12. HSQC spectrum of (12) in d_6 -DMSO

2.7 Synthesis of *EEE-N* (**13**)

Scheme S6. Synthesis of (**13**)

(2,2',2'',3,3',3''-hexahydro-[5,5':7',5''-terthieno[3,4-b][1,4]dioxin]-2'-yl)methanol (**7**) 0.100 g (0.221 mmol) was dissolved in 7 ml of anhydrous DMF. Then, NaH 60% 0.062g (1.547 mmol, 7eq) was added and let stirring under nitrogen at room temperature for 4 hours. 2-Chloro-N,N-dimethylethylamine hydrochloride (**9**) 0.041g (0.287 mmol, 1.3eq) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. The solvent was then evaporated and the residue was dissolved in a solution Hexane:Acetonitrile 1:9 together with 0.5mL of Iodomethane. Stirring continued overnight at room temperature. The solution was poured onto the diethyl ether and a brownish precipitate was collected and washed with abundant solvent, to afford **13** in a 48% yield (0.070g). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO) δ 6.71 – 6.43 (m, 2H), 4.76 – 3.87 (m, 11H), 3.84 – 3.77 (m, 1H), 3.73 (dd, J = 10.5, 4.9 Hz, 1H), 3.57 (ddt, J = 7.0, 4.7, 2.1 Hz, 2H), 3.11 (s, 9H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO) δ 141.61, 141.14, 136.95, 136.45, 109.48, 109.20, 107.58, 107.45, 100.32, 100.22, 98.27, 98.21, 98.19, 98.10, 73.47, 73.41, 72.64, 69.23, 69.14, 69.40, 65.80, 65.70, 65.60, 65.47, 65.39, 65.23, 65.03, 65.01, 64.76, 56.64. HRMS (ESI) m/z: [M]⁺ calcd for C₂₄H₂₈O₇N₁S₃, 538.10224; found, 538.10151.

Figure S13. ^1H NMR spectrum of (13) in d_6 -DMSO

Figure S14. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of (13) in d_6 -DMSO

Figure S15. HSQC spectrum of **(13)** in d_6 -DMSO

3. Previous synthesis of ETE-S by Stavrinidou *et al.*³

Previous synthesis of ETE-S, published by Stavrinidou *et al.*³

Scheme S7. Synthesis of ETE-S reported by Stavrinidou *et al.*³

4. Electropolymerizations by cyclic voltammetry

Figure S16. Cyclic voltammetry of the four trimers **14-17** to obtain their electropolymerized films. Electropolymerizations were performed with 1mM solution in acetonitrile, using 0.1M of TBAHFP as the electrolyte.

The current increase between consecutive cycles shows the efficient electrodeposition. Note that although some of the electrodeposited polymers had the tendency to dissolve in the electrolyte during electrodeposition, thin polymeric films were finally formed for all materials, as proven by the film photos in Figure 1b.

5. ATR FT-IR spectra of chemically polymerized trimers 14-17

Figure S17. ATR FT-IR spectra of chemically polymerized trimers **14-17**.

ATR FT-IR spectra were collected for the aqueous dispersions of PETE-S, PETE-N, PEEE-S and PEEE-N. All polymers exhibit the characteristic peak of the thiophene ring stretching at 1410 cm⁻¹. The peaks that appear between 1300 and 1000 cm⁻¹ are related to the C-O stretching. In the spectra of PETE-S and PEEE-S the presence of the sulfonate group is confirmed by the strong symmetric stretching of the S=O group at 1260 cm⁻¹.

6. Films preparation and conductivity measurements

Drop casted films of the chemically polymerized trimers were prepared on round-shaped glass coverslips with a diameter of 1.5 cm. The coverslips were previously treated for 2 hours with a fresh piranha solution which was prepared mixing one part of H₂O₂ and another part of H₂SO₄. For each polymer film, 0.15 mL of freshly prepared polymer dispersion was gently deposited in the middle of the coverslip, forming a convex downward meniscus shape, and let dry at room temperature overnight. Conductivity measurements were performed using a Jandel RM3-AR four-point probing system. The conductivity values were derived after probing three different films, in more than three different areas per film.

Table S1. Conductivity values for the chemically polymerized trimers

Polymer	Sheet resistance (Ω sq ⁻¹)	Thickness (nm)	Conductivity (S cm ⁻¹)
PETE-S	1812	222	24.9
PETE-N	96792	210	0.5
PEEE-S	256	230	169.8
PEEE-N	24608	198	2.1

7. Self-polymerization of EEE-S at long reaction times

Figure S18. UV-Vis spectra of each neat ETE-S and EEE-S ($360\mu\text{M}$) were recorded after 5 min of mixing (Hour 1), followed by 4 hours (Hour 5) and 9 hours delay (Hour 10). Plots are averaged from 3 different wells on a microplate reader plate.

8. In-vitro polymerization

Solutions of 10 mM hydrogen peroxide (Sigma Aldrich, 30 wt. % in H₂O, ACS reagent), 1 mg mL⁻¹ Horse Radish Peroxidase (Sigma Aldrich, Type VI, essentially salt-free, lyophilized powder, ≥250 units mg⁻¹ solid (using pyrogallol)) and solutions of 1.5 mM of each trimer were freshly prepared in DI water. Each reactant has a concentration of 360 μM, 180 μM, 5 U mL⁻¹ for respectively the trimers, the hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), and the peroxidase (HRP). Solutions were prepared in duplicates and placed in two different microplate wells of the microplate reader (Biotek Synergy H1) that was used for the UV-vis characterization of the enzymatic *in-vitro* polymerization. Peroxidase was added just before the measurements to guarantee a similar reaction rate in every well. After 5 min of plate mixing, the UV-vis absorption spectra were recorded from 250 to 900 nm at a step of 5 nm. Absorption spectra were obtained after averaging the results obtained from the two similar wells and after subtracting the contribution from the plate and the solvent. A baseline correction was then performed for each spectrum.

9. In-vivo polymerization

Two months old (after seed germination) Bean plants (*Phaseolous Vulgaris*) were used for the *in-vivo* polymerization of the four trimers. A single root was immersed in an Eppendorf tube containing 1 mM trimer solution in DI water for 24 hours. During functionalization, the rest of the root system was kept in a commercial growth gel (SeedThru). The functionalization process took place within a greenhouse. After 24 hours of functionalization the root that was immersed in the trimer solution was cut from the plant with a new scalpel and placed in DI water to prevent dehydration. Optical characterization was performed with a Nikon SMZ1500 stereomicroscope. Both plane views and cross sections were examined.

10. Morphological characterizations by means of AFM

The surface morphology of the electropolymerized PETE-S, PETE-N, PEEE-S and PEEE-N films has been imaged by means of Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). The topography and phase images are presented in Figure S19. Data were acquired in the tapping mode. Image size is 2 μm x 2 μm in all cases. The PETE-S and PEEE-N films appear to exhibit a quite homogeneous surface, while the PETE-N film has large protrusions. The inhomogeneity induced by these protrusions is apparent throughout the whole film surface, as evidenced in Figure 1b. The PEEE-S film is very thin and we believe that the inhomogeneous surface observed in the AFM images is related to a partial coverage of the ITO/glass substrate.

Figure S19. AFM topography and phase images of the electropolymerized PETE-S, PETE-N, PEEE-S and PEEE-N films. The image size is 2 μm x 2 μm in all cases.

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